

Lung Single-Cell Transcriptomics in Alpha-1 Antitrypsin Deficiency

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To the Editor:

Alpha-1 antitrypsin deficiency (AATD) is associated with an increased risk for emphysema in adults, owing to the reduced opposition to lung proteases such as neutrophil elastase. Severe AATD is usually caused by two copies of the (PI)*Z allele of the *SERPINA1* gene (PI*ZZ genotype). Heterozygous carriers of the PI*Z allele (PI*MZ) have an increased risk of airflow obstruction, particularly in cigarette smokers (1), though not as high as homozygous individuals. The AATD gene expression signature across lung cell types is not fully understood. This study sought to examine this signature using publicly available single-cell RNA-sequencing data.

Lung single-cell RNA-sequencing (scRNA-seq) data from a study of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) by Sauler and colleagues (2, 3) were obtained from the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO: GSE136831) and the Short Read Archive (SRA: SRP395406). Phenotypic data for each subject includes age, sex, race and ever-smoker and COPD status (3). The focus was on data from the 17 former smokers with COPD. Using the scRNA-seq read files from the SRA as the source of genetic data, the single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) rs28929474 provided the *SERPINA1* Z allele, and the S (rs17580), I (rs28931570) and F (rs28929470) alleles were also examined to determine the *SERPINA1* genotype (4). Cell types with zero cell counts for any of the MZ and ZZ subjects were excluded. The cleaned expression data were collapsed into gene-by-subject matrices for each cell type, creating a pseudobulk dataset. Associations between pseudobulk gene expression and *SERPINA1* Z allele dosage were tested using DESeq2 (5), with the covariates age and sex. Pathway analyses were performed for results in the each cell type using Gene Set Enrichment Analysis (GSEA) and the hallmark gene sets from MSigDB (6). Networks were created to highlight cell-cell relationships based on shared canonical pathway activity. Additional details regarding methods are available in the online data supplement.

Two subjects were found to be heterozygous for the S allele (MS genotype) and were removed, leaving 11 MM genotype subjects, one MZ subject and three ZZ subjects (Table E1). After data cleaning, scRNA-seq data were available for 38,387 cells and 41,240 genes across 15 subjects and 29 cell types (Tables E2 and E3). Higher *SERPINA1* expression was observed in macrophages, alveolar epithelial type II cells and monocytes in the bar plot of mean expression across cell types (Figure E1) and when comparing the UMAP plots with cell type labels or *SERPINA1* expression shading (Figure E2).

The largest number of differentially expressed genes (FDR < 0.05) in the tests of association between the pseudobulk expression and the Z allele dosage was in alveolar macrophages (72 genes; Tables 1 and E4). Volcano plots were created using the differential gene expression (DGE) results for alveolar macrophages and interstitial macrophages (Figures 1A and 1B). The top results for alveolar macrophages included the genes *CXCL8*, *CXCL2* and *IL6*. Intersecting the DGE results with the COPD case-control findings by Adams and colleagues in this scRNA-seq dataset (3), only the *ARF6* gene was found significant in both alveolar macrophage analyses, suggesting a possible overlap in disease-relevant vesicular trafficking. For interstitial macrophages, the top differentially expressed gene was *FOS* (Table 1 and Figure 1B). The genes *IL6* (Figure E3) and *IL1B* were also differentially expressed in interstitial macrophages. Although not statistically significant at FDR < 0.05, we

observed nominal differential expression ($p=0.009$) of *SERPINA1* in goblet cells.

In the networks (Figures 1C and 1D) and heatmaps (Figures E4 and E5) created using the pathway enrichment results in each cell type, up regulation of several pathways was observed in alveolar macrophages, in particular the tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNFA) signaling pathway (TNFA_SIGNALING_VIA_NFKB) and INFLAMMATORY_RESPONSE pathways. The *TNFA* pathway was also up regulated in several other cell types, including alveolar epithelial cells and monocytes. Although not accompanied by significant differential expression among individual genes, several pathways were down regulated in T cells, including the interferon gamma and alpha in CD4+ T cells, unfolded protein response and oxidative phosphorylation pathways.

Alpha-1 Antitrypsin has anti-inflammatory properties (7). The role of *TNFA* signaling in AATD inflammation and COPD (8) was supported by the observed *TNFA* pathway up-regulation with Z allele dosage across several cell types. Alveolar macrophages were observed to have the highest *SERPINA1* expression and also had the highest *TNFA* pathway and gene up-regulation, aligned with their overall role in AATD (9). Both *IL-6* and *CXCL8* were up-regulated and are pro-inflammatory cytokines capable of recruiting neutrophils. Increased expression of *NFKBIZ* and the *TNFA* pathway may also reflect altered proportion of alveolar macrophage subsets that are skewed towards proinflammatory spectrum, such as traditionally designated M2 subset. The presence of *CD83*, an activation marker that was recently reported as an inflammation checkpoint molecule (10), in the top results suggests it may be of interest in future experiments. Although AATD does not directly affect T cells (11), differential pathway activity with Z dosage was observed, adding insight to the observations of increased lymphocytes in AATD COPD (12). The impact on host interactions with the lung microbiome from these inflammatory effects in AATD is a current area of interest.

Limitations of this study include the small population of MZ and ZZ subjects, limiting the power to detect differentially expressed genes, and the lack of neutrophil data that would have provided greater disease pathobiological context (13). An enrichment of macrophages was present in the data, as outlined by Sauler and colleagues (2). When assessing the *SERPINA1* expression across cell types, the normalized data for each subject is compositional, so the levels should not be viewed as absolute.

This study has revealed genes and pathways relevant to AATD across lung cell types. We found proinflammatory changes, such as enrichment of *TNFA* signaling, even in cell types with low *SERPINA1* expression, demonstrating pervasive changes driven by AATD. Together these findings may help improve the molecular understanding of AATD in the lung and inform future therapeutic endeavors, including experiments in cytokine-related therapies (14, 15).

Competing interests

No competing interests were disclosed for Dr. Morrow.

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Data Availability

Data were obtained from:

Gene Expression Omnibus Accession: GSE136831

Short Read Archive Study: SRP395406

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Table 1. Summary of significant differential gene expression results for *SERPINA1* Z allele dosage

Cell type	Total genes	Genes with p < 0.05	Genes with adjusted p-value < 0.05
Alveolar Macrophage	9,859	920	72 genes *
Interstitial Macrophage	3,995	303	26 genes *
Non-classical Monocyte	11,117	248	<i>KLF6</i> , <i>ZFP36</i> , <i>MIR222HG</i> , ENSG00000267519, ENSG00000274213
Classical Monocyte	4,120	241	<i>MT2P1</i> , <i>MTCO1P40</i> , <i>KLF6</i> , <i>ANKRD28</i> , <i>MBNL1</i> , <i>MT1E</i> , <i>ADD3</i> , <i>JUND</i> , <i>CAB39</i> , <i>CREM</i> , ENSG00000267519, ENSG00000274213
Goblet	8,880	183	<i>FOXO1</i>
Conventional Type 1 Dendritic	10,791	228	<i>GNG2</i>
Natural Killer	14,472	541	<i>MT2P1</i>
B	14,324	414	<i>FOS</i> , <i>ABCA1</i>
Myofibroblast	10,370	133	ENSG00000264281

* Figures 1A and 1B

(A)

(B)

(C)

(D)

Figure 1. Cell-type specific differential gene expression by Z allele dosage: (A) volcano plot of the results for alveolar macrophages, (B) volcano plot of the interstitial macrophage results, (C) bipartite network representation of the hallmark pathway enrichment findings across all cell types in up-regulated results and (D) down-regulated results, with node size proportional to number of edges (pathways = red squares, cell types = blue circles, AT1 = alveolar epithelial type I cells, AT2 = alveolar epithelial type II cells, cMonocyte = classical monocytes, ncMonocyte = non-classical monocyte, NK = natural killer cells, T_Cytotoxic = CD8 T cells, T_Regulatory = CD4 T cells, VE_Venous = vascular endothelial venous cells from Sauler et al. (2))